

The UrbObsBel project - Towards Understanding Light Pollution in Urban Environments

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DOI:

Abstract: The UrbObsBel project's primary goal is to establish Serbia's first modern urban observatory, as an addition to the existing Astronomical Observatory of Belgrade, with the main purpose of monitoring, analyzing, and researching a topic that has received very little scientific attention in Serbia - light pollution. The measurements are carried out in two entirely different environments - one in the highly urbanized area (Belgrade), and the other in the dark, rural setting at Vidojevica Mountain, which holds an Astronomical station used for scientific research. This approach will allow researchers to more accurately assess light pollution distribution, its sources, and its effects on the environment. Measurements that are carried out in Belgrade are set on the highest point of the area, which allows a synoptic view of the city and its surroundings, enabling multilayered observations in different time scales - from rapid changes to seasonal and yearly variations. Various devices are used to gather data, such as TESS-W, Sky Quality Meter, AllSky Camera, custom-built visible and near-infrared (VNIR) hyperspectral imaging sensors, and the Teledyne FLIR A700 thermal camera, providing different data on light propagation and its characteristics. Combining the material obtained from two observational units, set in urbanized and rural areas, will allow researchers to measure how much human activity contributes to the degradation of natural darkness, in which manner the artificial light propagates in the atmosphere in urban areas, how light pollution changes during the night, seasons or year, ultimately leading to proposal of strategies that can tackle light pollution and its temporal variations.

Started in January 2024, with three-year duration, this research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (grant no. 6775, Urban Observatory of Belgrade – UrbObsBel).

Keywords: urban observatory; light pollution; tess-w; sqm; allsky camera; urbanization.

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